

A REVIEW OF THE ARANEIDAE GENERA AND SPECIES IN SOUTH AFRICA (ARACHNIDA: ARANEAE)

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ABSTRACT: South Africa has a rich fauna of Araneidae, with 112 species across 40 genera listed on the South African National Spider Species list. Since the publication of the Araneidae Photo Identification Guides, several changes have been published, supported by new distribution records from iNaturalist. However, except for the species that have been confirmed and are listed for South Africa in the World Spider Catalogue, several species remain of uncertain identification or are completely unknown. Updated data show that 22% Araneidae species are South African endemics with 62 species (55.4%) found throughout Africa, and 16 species (4%) have a wide distribution beyond Africa. But several recorded species remain to be identified, and the expected number of Araneidae species could be as high as 140.

Keywords: biodiversity, cosmopolitan, introduced, South African National Survey (SANSa)

INTRODUCTION

Biodiversity is one of the most important concepts in contemporary biology, with a broad range of applications. In South Africa, the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) was initiated in 1997 with the primary aim of documenting and describing the arachnid fauna. During the SANSa surveys, large numbers of Araneidae spiders were sampled and need to be identified to address conservation issues. Only a few araneid genera in South Africa have been revised, complicating identification. Some of the revisions were by Emerit (1973), who revised the Gasteracanthinae of South Africa; Grasshoff (1984), who revised *Caerostris* and *Neoscona* (Grasshoff, 1986); and Bjørn (1997), who revised the *Argiope* species.

Pycnacantha tribulus (Fabricius, 1781) was the first Araneidae species described from South Africa more than 240 years ago (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024). Since then, numerous species have been added to the species list.

- In 2010, in the first Spider Atlas of South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010), 101 Araneidae species from 38 genera were listed with distribution maps.
- In 2022, in the three Araneidae Photo Identification Guides (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022 a-c), 105 species were discussed.
- In 2023, with the publication of the first checklist of spiders of South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023), 100 species were listed. Five *Araneus* species described by Strand (1907, 1909) were listed as nomen dubium in the World Spider Catalog (2026) and subsequently removed from the list (Nentwig *et al.*, 2019).
- In the 2026 Spider National list, as well as the World Spider Catalog (2026) for South Africa, there are 112 araneid species listed. The increased species numbers were due to the discovery of species known from Africa also occurring in South Africa (Table 2). However, there are still about eight species recorded from South Africa but of which the identity still need to be confirm (see pp. 12-13) as well as 13 unknown species (p.14).

ARANEIDAE: SOUTH AFRICAN ENDEMIC SPECIES

In Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2010), 26 Araneidae species were listed as endemic to South Africa. Thirteen of these endemic species were described between 1781 and 1907, only with brief descriptions and no drawings, complicating identification.

Five of the species were described by Simon (1895, 1897, 1903), and four of them were recollected and redescribed (Table 1). However, of the old species, there are still two: *Nemospiza conspiciata* Simon, 1903 and *Araneus graemii* Pocock, 1900, which have not been recollected. The five species of Strand (1907, 1909) were listed as nomen dubium (Nentwig *et al.*, 2019) and removed from the list, resulting in the number of endemic species declining to 20 as listed in Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2023).

Based on iNaturalist records, there are now only 16 species on the South African endemic list (Table 1). Species like *Araneus coccinella* Pocock, 1898; *Cladomelea akermani* Hewitt, 1923; *Nemoscolus elongatus* Lawrence, 1947; *Pycnacantha tribulus* (Fabricius, 1781) and *Singa albidorsata* Kauri, 1950 have a wider distribution as South Africa.

TABLE 1. List of 16 Araneidae species that are endemic to South Africa with references for further reading.

SPECIES	FURTHER READING
<i>Araneus graemii</i> Pocock, 1900	WSC not recollected
<i>Araneus haploscapellus</i> (Strand, 1907)	Listed as nomen dubium but recollected see p. 12.
<i>Araneus varus</i> (Kauri, 1950)	Marusik (2017); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Caerostris tinamaze</i> Gregorič, 2015	Gregorič <i>et al.</i> (2015); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Cladomelea debeeri</i> Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2004	Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2004); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Gastroxya benoiti</i> Emerit, 1973	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022b)
<i>Ideocaira transversa</i> Simon, 1903	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb (2024).
<i>Ideocaira triquetra</i> Simon, 1903	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022b)
<i>Isoxya yatesi</i> Emerit, 1973	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2025)
<i>Larinia natalensis</i> (Grasshoff, 1971)	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022b)
<i>Nemoscolus obscurus</i> Simon, 1897	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022c)
<i>Nemospiza conspiciata</i> Simon, 1903	WSC not recollected
<i>Paralarinia bartelsi</i> (Lessert, 1933)	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022c)
<i>Pasilobus dippenaarae</i> Roff & Haddad, 2015	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022c); Roff & Haddad (2015)
<i>Singafrotypa mandela</i> Kuntner & Hormiga, 2002	Kuntner & Hormiga (2002); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022c)
<i>Ursa turbinata</i> Simon, 1895	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022c)

ARANEIDAE: AFRICAN ENDEMIC SPECIES

Presently, 62 species (55.4%) are recorded throughout Africa frequently outside its type locality (Table 2). Araneidae spiders, especially juveniles and small-bodied species, use ballooning to travel across grasslands, savannas, deserts, and forests. Ballooning allows spiders to cross long stretches of open plains where walking would be inefficient. This is especially important in Africa, where habitats can be widely spaced and are frequently disturbed by fire, grazing, or seasonal flooding. Spiders also use electric fields to launch even when winds are calm, common during early morning or storm-related atmospheric changes.

Africa’s wet–dry seasons create cycles of resource abundance and scarcity. It enables spiders to move between isolated patches of suitable habitat, promoting genetic mixing and recolonisation after environmental stress.

Africa’s natural disturbance cycles help drive spider dispersal. Frequent fires in savannas and grasslands clear vegetation. Spiders then recolonize rapidly by ballooning, repopulating burned areas. Similar behaviour is noted globally, including mass aerial escapes during disasters.

TABLE 2. Araneidae species endemic to Africa that has also recorded from South Africa since 2020. Distribution data from the World Spider Catalog.

SPECIES	DISTRIBUTION	FURTHER READING
1. <i>Acantharachne seydeli</i> Giltay, 1935	Congo (DRC), South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022e)
2. <i>Aethriscus olivaceus</i> Pocock, 1902	Congo (DRC), South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
3. <i>Acusilas africanus</i> Simon, 1895	Cameroon, Congo (DRC), Gabon, Sierra Leone, Tanzania, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
4. <i>Afracantha camerunensis</i> (Thorell, 1899)	Cameroon, Congo (DRC), Ghana, Swaziland, Botswana, Zambia, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021b)
5. <i>Arachnura scorpionoides</i> Vinson, 1863	Congo (DRC), Ethiopia, Madagascar, Mauritius, Seychelles, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020a)
6. <i>Araneus holzapfelae</i> Lessert, 1936	Mozambique, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord (2020)
7. <i>Araneus tatianea</i> Lessert, 1938	Congo (DRC), South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
8. <i>Argiope tapinolobata</i> Bjørn, 1997	Senegal, Namibia, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
9. <i>Bijoaaraneus legonensis</i> (Grasshoff & Edmunds, 1979)	Ghana, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022d)
10. <i>Cladomelea longipes</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1877)	Cameroon, Congo (DRC), Zimbabwe, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord (2019)
12. <i>Cyrtarachne finniganae</i> Lessert, 1936	Mozambique, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman (2026)
13. <i>Cyrtarachne termitophila</i> Lawrence, 1952	Congo (DRC), South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman (2026)
14. <i>Cyrtophora petersi</i> Karsch, 1878	Mozambique, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
15. <i>Hypsacantha crucimaculata</i> (Dahl, 1914)	Congo (DRC), Mozambique, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022b)
16. <i>Isoxya mossamedensis</i> Benoit, 1962	Angola, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022b)
17. <i>Isoxya mucronata</i> Walckenaer, 1841	Congo (DRC), South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022b)
18. <i>Mahemba hewitti</i> (Lessert, 1930)	Congo (DRC), South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022b)
19. <i>Neoscona kisangani</i> Grasshoff, 1986	Congo (DRC), South Africa	Booyesen & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2025)
20. <i>Paraplectana thorn-toni</i> (Blackwall, 1865)	Mozambique, South Africa	Du Preez & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2022)
21. <i>Poltys monstrosus</i> Simon, 1897	Mozambique, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Uys (2025)

Araneus tatianea

Isoxya mucronata

Poltys monstrosus

Bijoaaraneus legonensis

Araneus holzapfelae

Mahemba hewitti

ARANEIDAE: COSMOPOLITAN AND INTRODUCED SPECIES

Sixteen Araneidae species recorded from South Africa have a distribution range that extends beyond Africa (Table 3). This includes species with a broad natural range as well as those that have expanded through human activity. Introduced species, also called aliens, non-native, exotic, or foreign species, are species that arrive in a new area through deliberate or accidental human transport, rather than through natural dispersal.

Many of these species are regarded as naturalised when they are non-native to an area but have established self-sustaining populations that survive, reproduce, and spread without ongoing human assistance. When their geographic range extends across most or all regions of the world, they are known as cosmopolitan species.

TABLE 3. Araneidae species that have a wider distribution beyond Africa that was possibly introduced into South Africa. Distribution data from the World Spider Catalog.

SPECIES	DISTRIBUTION	FUTHER READING
1. <i>Argiope lobata</i> (Pallas, 1772)	Southern Europe to Central Asia and China, Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
2. <i>Argiope trifasciata</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	North, Central and South America. Introduced to St. Helena, Africa, Portugal to Israel	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
3. <i>Cyclosa conica</i> (Pallas, 1772)	America, Europe, Turkey, Caucasus, Russia, Europe to Far East, Iran, Central Asia, China. Introduced to South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Zyl (2023)
4. <i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	Mediterranean to Japan, India to Papua New Guinea, Australia. Introduced to St. Helena, South Africa, Eswatini	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
5. <i>Cyclosa oculata</i> (Walckenaer, 1802)	Europe to Far East, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, China. Introduced to South Africa, Hawaii	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
6. <i>Cyrtarachne ixoides</i> (Simon, 1870)	Mediterranean, Caucasus, South Africa, Madagascar	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones (2008)
7. <i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	Widespread in subtropical and tropical areas of Asia, Africa, Australia, and in the warm coastal Mediterranean areas of Europe	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2025)
8. <i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889)	Pakistan, India, Thailand, China, Taiwan, Philippines, Indonesia. Introduced to South Africa, Eswatini	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021a)
9. <i>Hyposinga pygmaea</i> (Sundevall, 1831)	North America, Europe, Turkey, Israel, Caucasus, Russia (Europe to Far East), Iran, Central Asia, China, Korea, Japan. Introduced to South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021b)
10. <i>Larinia chloris</i> (Audouin, 1826)	Spain, Greece, Cyprus, Turkey, North and East Africa to Israel, Iraq, Iran, India, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh. Introduced to Mozambique, South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021b)
11. <i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	Widespread throughout Africa. Introduced to the Caribbean, Colombia, Venezuela to Argentina	Jones & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2022a)
12. <i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	Southern Europe, St. Helena, Africa, Turkey, Middle East, Ukraine, Caucasus, Russia (Europe) to Central Asia	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021c)
13. <i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	Cape Verde, Africa to India	Jones & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2022b)
14. <i>Neoscona vigilans</i> (Blackwall, 1865)	Widespread throughout Africa to the Philippines and New Guinea	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021c)
15. <i>Nephilingis cruentata</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Tropical South America, tropical and subtropical Africa, Indian Ocean Islands, Asia, Australia	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021c)
16. <i>Pararaneus spectator</i> (Karsch, 1885)	East, Central, and South Africa; Yemen; Sinai (Egypt) and Israel	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021c)

Cyrtarachne ixoides

Cyclosa conica

Eriovixia excelsa

Hyposinga pygmaea

Cyclosa oculata

ARANEID SPECIES AND GENERA OBSERVED IN SOUTH AFRICA BUT STILL UNNAMED

The Araneidae is one of the spider families that are very frequently seen in the field and even in gardens. Especially on iNaturalist, they are frequently photographed, but without examination of the genitalia, the specimens are frequently impossible to identify to species level.

From the literature, especially the work of Dr Levi, we have found some look-alikes. We hope that showing all these images will help with species recognition or even encourage people to collect specimens. Presently, we only suggest preliminary generic and species-level identification, which still needs to be confirmed.

- **Cf *Araneus haploscapellus* (Strand, 1907)?**

WAKEFIELD KZN

UMHLANGA

- **Cf *Araneus detrimentosus* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1889)?**

After Levi (1973)

WOODBUSH

JEFFREYSBAY

- **Cf *Araneus partitus* (Walckenaer, 1841)?**

After Levi (1973)

IRENE

- **Cf *Molinaranea phaethontis* (Simon, 1896)?**

Female from Gondwana Private Game Reserve. Credit: Jolandi Buck.

• **ACANTHEPEIRA Marx, 1883?**

After Levi (1976)

ASD

Peter Webb

LEKGALAMEETSE NR

Linda Wiese

• **CHORIZOPEOIDES Mi & Wang, 2018?**

Chorizopesoides orientalis After Mi & Wang (2018).

SOUTPANSBERG

ASD

Wynand Uys

HOEDSPRUIT

• **ZYGIELLA F.O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1902**

After Levi (1972)

Linda Wiese

JEFFREYSBAY

Linda Wiese

• **LARINIOIDES Caporiacco, 1934**

After Levi (1974)

Peter Webb

UMHLANGA

Linda Wiese

THYSPUNT

UNKNOWN SPECIES

CONCLUSION

Except for the species shown here, we have already identified new species within known genera, such as *Cyphalonotus*, *Gea*, *Ideocaira*, *Paraplectana*, *Pycnacantha*, and *Singa*. We will probably eventually have 140 or more species, many more than the 112 currently listed on the South African National Spider Species list. But we need taxonomists and specimens in collections.

But what to do in the meantime? On iNaturalist, these unknowns can maybe be listed under the genera as suggested here. At least if the identification problems are solved, the species distribution records are available.

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